

Nuclear Conversion:**An Obligatory Choice for the Sustainability and Safety of Human Life on Earth***Dr. R. Morelli¹ TCM AICE/ICEC, IEng MIET**Nuclear For Peace Association Board, AICE/ICEC Scientific Commission Member,
Environment and Society Association Scientific Committee, Civilization of Love Committee Board***• Introduction**

The following analysis is developed exclusively on data and contents of official documents, produced by recognized institutions or organizations. These documents can be consulted through the links at the bottom, or among the references and on the individual graphs, images or tables used below to facilitate understanding. Nuclear conversion is understood here as the dilution of highly enriched uranium (up to 95% .particularly for military purposes) to transform it into nuclear fuel for peaceful purposes (4%), together with the plutonium produced in the reprocessing of spent fuel. In other words: it is about converting armaments into energy for human development. The purpose of the analysis conducted herein is aimed at demonstrating that the Nuclear Conversion is a forced choice by criteria of sustainability and safety, which does not find technical feasibility obstacles as there is a similar successful precedent in the *Megatons to Megawatts Program*². Moreover, this choice, while serving the reasons for disarmament and human development, appears to be the obligatory path for the sustainability and security of life on Earth, given the demands placed on the energy transition and given the armament policies of the great powers have led to a huge accumulation of fissile material, already transformed or transformable in a short time into nuclear devices, precisely at a time when nuclear war has become a constant threat.

• Analysis on various topics**• For a comparison of "nuclear" with other technologies (Fig. 2 and Tab. 3)**

(Fig. 2) After years of uncertainty and reticence, the inclusion of "nuclear" in the list of eco-sustainable economic activities in the EU taxonomy was an explicit recognition of the impossibility of an energy transition without this technology. It - based on fissile fuels (uranium and plutonium) - not only can allow the energy transition, but allows it in more realistic times, bringing undeniable environmental benefits, in terms of reduced volumes and weights of fuels used and lower carbonaceous and sulfurous gas emissions, particulate and solid waste, if compared, for the same amount of energy produced with technologies based on fossil fuels. Fig. 2 below compares the quantities of fuel needed in the case of uranium and in the case of coal to produce 8000 kWh of electricity (about double what an average Italian family consumes). In the case of uranium, a variable quantity of ore between 30 and 70 kg is enough from which 230 g of concentrated uranium oxide U_3O_8 are obtained, which can be used as fuel in a CANDU reactor (a Canadian technology that uses heavy water D_2O , as moderator to slow the fission neutrons to their optimum point, and natural uranium, without enrichment, as fuel). After use in the reactor, the 230 g, which have become more radioactive due to the fission products contained, except for a negligible loss of mass transformed into energy, are stored in a special warehouse, but still contain a large part of material which can be made fertile from a nuclear and therefore productive point of view. If the 230 g of U_3O_8 were to be used in a light water reactor (LWR), they would need enrichment; process that would produce 30 g of enriched uranium and 200 g of process by-products. After producing 8000 kWh these 30 g of enriched uranium would become spent (but largely still fertilizable) fuel, and there would be 20 ml of highly radioactive waste, plus 6 g of glass for their vitrification. If, on the other hand, we wanted to

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² E.g. refer to. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Megatons_to_Megawatts_Program

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produce 8000 kWh with coal, we would need 3 t of anthracite, the coal with the highest calorific value, which after combustion would produce 300 kg of fly ash, gaseous emissions equal to 8 t, essentially CO₂ and SO₂, as well as micro- inhalable particles (PM2.5 – PM5) .

Fig.2

(Tab. 3) It should be noted that apart from civil works, and therefore concrete, "nuclear" compared to some other technologies, minimizes the quantity of materials per unit of installed power (especially the most valuable ones) , thanks to greater scale effects and more advanced technologies, thus limiting the environmental/extraction and consumption impact, both on the global resources available and on the local supply territories.

Tab.3 PWR material input requirements per kWth

Material	kg / kW
Concrete	180 – 560
Carbon steel	10 – 65
Wood	4.7 – 5.6
Stainless steel	1.56 – 2.10
Galvanized iron	1.26
PVC	0.80 – 1.27
Insulation	0.70 – 0.92
Copper	0.69 – 2.00
Uranium	0.40 – 0.62
Manganese	0.33 – 0.70
Zirconium	0.20 – 0.40
Chromium	0.15 – 0.55
Nickel	0.10 – 0.50
Inconel	0.10 – 0.12
Brass / bronze	0.04
Lead	0.03 – 0.05
Aluminum	0.02 – 0.24
Silver	0.01
Cadmium	0.01
Boron	0.01
Indium	0.01
Total	195 - 635

Source:

<https://www.energy.gov/sites/default/files/2022-02/Nuclear%20Energy%20Supply%20Chain%20Report%20-%20Final.pdf>

- **The fuel cycle and the possible fertilization of residual *spent fuel* (Fig. 4 and 4')**

(Fig. 4) To proceed further with our reasoning, it is necessary to illustrate the nuclear fuel cycle. It shows how: 1) Uranium oxide mineral U_3O_8 (yellow cake) is converted to uranium fluoride UF_6 and then enriched in fissile content. Converted to uranium dioxide UO_2 (usually in sintered pellets) is introduced in a metal casing (e.g. austenitic nickel-chromium based superalloys resistant to corrosive/radiative environments in high temperatures/pressures) and sent for the proper manufacture of nuclear fuel. After its use: 2) The *spent fuel* leaving the reactor can be stored or sent to reprocessing, where the plutonium is separated from the still useful uranium. It is worth remembering here - in these times of energy shortage, when we worry about the *energy poverty* of families - that on average, even the spent fuel, after a cycle in a reactor, still contains 2% of fissile material and the 95% of material that can become fertile. All existing fissile material, including spent fuel, is therefore an energy reserve that is still only minimally exploited today.

Fig.4

(Fig 4') For further details, please refer to the following figure and to the document from which it was taken (see the relative link shown in the figure).

Fig.4'

• **Availability of uranium resources (Fig. 5, 5' and Tab.5,1, 5.2)**

(Fig. 5) The distribution of natural uranium resources, however, is not favorable to the EU, which is substantially devoid of them, and this requires, among the energy security criteria, policies for the diversification of primary energy sources and of their supply chains, as well as diversification of the technological supply chains for the production of electricity. Furthermore, under the growing global pressure of the use of nuclear power, exploration and research of new deposits, or recovery of old ones - albeit at increasing extraction prices - are to be encouraged, together with research for the use of breeder reactors and the burning of fission materials such as plutonium, or other fissionable materials such as thorium.

Figure 14. Global distribution of uranium resources⁴⁸

Source: <https://www.energy.gov/sites/default/files/2022-02/Nuclear%20Energy%20Supply%20Chain%20Report%20-%20Final.pdf>

Fig.5

Quantities of mineral resources are greater than commonly perceived and correlate with both market prices and the cost of extraction. The world's known uranium resources have increased by at least a quarter in the last decade due to increased mineral exploration. The following table shows the availability of uranium resources by country in 2021 (source WNN <https://world-nuclear.org/information-library/nuclear-fuel-cycle/uranium-resources/supply-of-uranium.aspx>)

Tab.5.1	tonnes U	percentage of world
Australia	1,684,100	28%
Kazakhstan	815,200	13%
Canada	588,500	10%
Russia	480,900	8%
Namibia	470,100	8%
South Africa	320,900	5%
Niger	311,100	5%
Brazil	276,800	5%
China	223,900	4%
Mongolia	144,600	2%
Uzbekistan	131,300	2%
Ukraine	107,200	2%
Botswana	87,200	1%
USA	59,400	1%
Tanzania	58,200	1%
Jordan	52,500	1%
Other	266,600	5%
World total	6,078,500	

In practice, even if mineral explorations were to increase with increasing extractive costs, the available quantity of uranium would increase, albeit at a higher price. From the same WNN source mentioned above, it can be seen that the current possible correlation between resource availability and extraction cost is as follows:

Known Uranium Resources and Exploration Expenditure

Fig.5'

The WNN estimate (see cited source) of the cumulative historical production of uranium, from 1945 to 2022, i.e. in 77 years, is 3,1 Million tU as follows:

Tab. 5.2		Cumulative production (tU)
Kazakhstan/Uzbekistan		594,795
Canada		554,475
United States		374,947
Australia		240,771
Germany		217,161
Russia		181,769
South Africa		165,678
Niger		156,620
Namibia		152,214
Czech Republic		111,214
France		77,015
Ukraine		70,131
China		59,499
Others		149,474
Total		3,109,675

- Uranium and plutonium for civil and military uses - Trend of recent historical data (Fig.6, 6',8,9,11.12; Tab.6.1, 7,10)

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(Fig. 6) The “balance of terror” based on nuclear weaponry following Hiroshima, World War II and the resulting Cold War, has caused a buildup of fissile material for military and civilian purposes: essentially enriched uranium (HEU) and Plutonium (Pu) separated in the reprocessing of nuclear fuel. The situation for plutonium up to 2010 is illustrated here together with that of spent fuel.

Figure 5.5. World spent-fuel and plutonium discharges from power reactors by decade, 1961–2010

Source:
<https://www.sipri.org/sites/default/files/files/books/SIPRI97AIBeWa/SIPRI97AIBeWa.pdf>

Fig.6

In terms of plutonium, but also of enriched uranium, the destructive atomic potential present on Earth has thus increased immeasurably. This potential is obviously proportional to the quantity of fissile materials accumulated over time, which however also constitutes a strong reserve of energy for peaceful purposes, which can be conveniently extracted only through nuclear fission, in special reactors of various types. Nuclear fission technology, therefore, is not only for the use of an energy source, but also and above all the only convenient way - available today - to get rid of the destructive potential accumulated over time for military purposes. These two basic reasons, linked to the sustainability and safety of human life on Earth - exposed especially in our time to threats of nuclear war by belligerent nuclear powers - lead us to consider Nuclear Conversion (i.e. the conversion of military fissile into electrical energy) as an instrument of peace and development for all humanity. The feasibility of the conversion process has already been proven in the past by the Megatons to Megawatts Program, completed in 2013 with the conversion of thousands of nuclear warheads into electricity.

If we look at the military use of fissile material with an eye to sustainability, there is no argument to support it, since they are instruments of mass destruction. Furthermore, the relationship between the destructive potential of a nuclear device and the amount of fissile material needed to make it, is very complex and depends on many factors (see Fig, 6'), but can highlight other very negative aspects. By way of example, the following two well-known cases of the bombs on Hiroshima and Nagasaki are reported, from which it can be seen that only few percents of fissile material mass is actually used for the explosion, while the remainder is dispersed in the environment. It should be remembered, in the case of the use of plutonium dispersed in the environment, as in Nagasaki, that it is not only a radioactive material, but a highly toxic one. A few inhaled micrograms are enough for immediate death or fractions of micrograms for

lung cancer. Not to mention the real waste of useful fissile material for producing energy in an energy-hungry world, where at least 1 billion people still lack access to electricity and water.

Bomb	Yield		Notes	Weight of nuclear material
	kt TNT	TJ		
Hiroshima's "Little Boy" gravity bomb	13–18	54–75	Gun type uranium-235 fission bomb (the first of the two nuclear weapons that have been used in warfare).	64 kg of Uranium-235, about 1.38% of the uranium fissioned
Nagasaki's "Fat Man" gravity bomb	19–23	79–96	Implosion type plutonium-239 fission bomb (the second of the two nuclear weapons used in warfare).	6.2 kg of Plutonium-239, about 1 kg fissioned

Tab.6.1

Hereinafter is a graph for an approximate estimate between the weight and destructive potential of nuclear devices - source https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/4/4a/US_nuclear_weapons_yield-to-weight_comparison.svg

Fig.6'

As can be seen in the tables that follow, inventories of enriched uranium and plutonium for military uses are of such dimensions (hundreds and tens of hundreds of tons, respectively) that the accumulated destructive power could destroy life on Earth forever, not just for effect of the so-called "nuclear winter", but also for the levels of radioactivity and toxicity that would be reached in a generalized way, as well as for fallout effects. Assuming that there are no effects on the stability of the Earth's atmosphere, which is completely improbable.

(Tab 7) The table shown here is produced on RECNA data. It shows the distribution of plutonium among different countries, both for military and civilian uses. Plutonium can be used for the production of

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electricity in a suitable mixture with uranium (MOX = Mixed Oxide). Despite its strong toxicity and fissility, plutonium is a valuable source of energy when integrated into the nuclear fuel cycle both the one normally produced in power reactors and the one coming from decommissioned nuclear weapons. In a conventional nuclear reactor, one kilogram of Pu-239 can produce enough heat to generate nearly 8 million kilowatt-hours of electricity.

Distribution per Country of Total Separated Pu (Tons)																
Country	Military		Non Military		Military		Non Military		Military		Non Military		Military		Non Military	
Russia	94	84	94	86.8	94	89.4	94	91.5	94	93	88	101.3	88	103.1		
US	44.9	43.4	38.3	49.3	38.3	49.3	38.4	49.4	38.4	49.4	38.4	49.3	38.4	49.3		
France	6	60.2	6	61.9	6	63.4	6	65.4	6	65.4	6	67.7	6	74.8		
China	1.8	0.01	1.8	0.03	1.8	0.03	2.9	0.04	2.9	0.04	2.9	0	2.9	0.04		
UK	7.3	99.9	3.2	103.3	3.2	106.2	3.2	110.3	3.2	113	3.2	115.8	3.2	115.8		
Israel	0.84		0.86		0.88		0.9		0.92		0.92		0.96			
Pakistan	0.15		0.19		0.22		0.28		0.31		0.37		0.41			
India	5.12	0.2	5.69	0.4	6.19	0.4	6.58	0.4	7.07	0.4	7.1		8.4	0.4		
North Korea	0.03		0.03		0.03		0.04		0.4		0.4		0.04			
Japan		47.1		47.8		47.9		47		47.3		45.7		45.5		
Germany				2.1		1.8		0.5								
Other Countries		5		2.9		2.4		1.8		1.6		1.9		0.7		
Sub-Total ~	160.3	340.1	150.1	354.5	150.6	360.8	152.3	366.3	152.8	370.1	150	380	148	390		
Year	2015		2016		2017		2018		2019		2020		2021			
Total~	500.4		504.6		511.4		518.6		522.9		530		538			
Source:	https://www.recna.nagasaki-u.ac.jp/recna/en-fmdata/pu_2021											RECNA Fissile Material Data Monitoring Team				

Our elaboration on RECNA data

Tab.7

(Fig. 8) The map of the location of accumulated plutonium, both for military and civilian uses, indicates that it is predominantly held in Eurasia. Military use of plutonium is prevalent in Russia, while its civilian use is prevalent in the Western world.

Source: https://www.recna.nagasaki-u.ac.jp/recna/en-fmdata/pu_2021

Fig.8

(Fig. 9) Historically, plutonium has a constantly growing inventory and only recently has its use in nuclear fuel been resorted to through MOX. The following graph shows the constant increasing trend and its

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growth rate globally (~5.4 Tons/Year). The EU seems to have abandoned this field of research while in the East (Russia and China) they are even cooperating on innovative reactors. This suggests the need to reflect on whether to resume/strengthen research on direct use in innovative reactors that can burn PU and/or HEU.

Our elaboration on RECNA data

Fig.9

(Tab. 10) The table shown here is produced on RECNA data. It shows the distribution of highly enriched uranium among different countries, both for military and civilian uses. The HEU can be burned directly in CFR-600 fast neutron reactors developed by Russia and the subject of recent cooperation with China. The composition of the CFR-600 fuel is not yet known, but it is thought that it may be similar to that of BN-600, which uses 17%, 21% and 26% enriched uranium. The CFR-600 is a plant that according to some observers could play a fundamental role in increasing armaments being able to produce fuel for about 50 nuclear warheads a year. In the current context in which nuclear wars are threatened, the risk to the sustainability and safety of human life on Earth is evident.

Distribution per Country of Total HEU (Tons)												
Country	Military	Non Military										
Russia	646	20	670	9	670	9	670	9	670	9	672	6
US	512	83	517	82	468.6	98.6	479.4	95.1	478.9	92.1	480	82
France	26	4.6	26	4.7	26	4.7	26	4.806	26	5.19	25	5.4
China	16		18	0.24	18	0.24	14	0.24	14	0.24	14	0.24
UK	19.8	1.4	19.8	1.398	19.8	1.398	19.8	1.37	19.8	1.24	21.9	0.7
Israel	0.3		0.3	0.002	0.3	0.002	0.3	0.002	0.3	0.022	0.3	0.3
Pakistan	3		3.1	0.017	3.3	0.017	3.4	0.017	3.6	0.017	3.7	3.9
India	2.4		3.2	0.005	3.6	0.005	4	0.005	4.4	0.005	4.4	5.2
North Korea			0.042		0.042		0.042		0.045		0.5	0.7
Non-nuclear Weapon Countries		15		15		15		15		15		15
Sub-Total	1226	124	1257	122.3	1210	128.9	1217	125.6	1217.5	122.8	1220	110
Year	2015		2016		2017		2018		2019		2021	
Total	1349.5		1379.7		1338.5		1342.5		1340.3		1330	

Source: our elaboration on data from https://www.recna.nagasaki-u.ac.jp/recna/en-fmdat.a/heu_2022

Tab.10

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(Fig. 11) The map of the dislocation of the accumulated HEU, both for military and civilian uses, indicates that it is predominantly held by Russia and secondly by the US. Military use of the HEU is prevalent in Russia, while its civilian use is prevalent in the Western world.

Source: <https://www.recn.nagasaki-u.ac.jp/recna/en-fmdata/mmap-heu-2021>

Fig.11

(Fig. 12) Contrarily to plutonium, which shows a growing inventory, enriched uranium shows a decreasing inventory (- 4.3 tons/year), which however is the result of a downward trend by the major nuclear powers, which actually adds up to that of a growth trend for small nuclear countries, especially those in the Asian area.

Source: our elaboration on data from https://www.recn.nagasaki-u.ac.jp/recna/en-fmdata/heu_2022

Fig.12

- **Comparison between supply and demand for: Uranium, Conversion, Enrichment; Use of fixed systems (Fig. 13)** A comparison in 2001, recently resumed, on the OECD Countries between demand and demand for Uranium, Conversion and Enrichment highlighted that the requests for uranium are far greater than the production, while there is excess Conversion and Enrichment capacity with respect to the requests that

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date. The foreseeable increased use of nuclear technology that has opened up in the energy transition after the Russia-Ukraine war and the consequent speculation on energy prices in Europe will further increase the gap between production and demand. It is therefore evident that the difference can be filled either by increasing the production of uranium, which however requires long times for reactivation/opening mines, or by resorting to accumulated fissile, especially that for military uses, which at least in the initial transitional phase will be able to bridge the differences through the dilution of the available HEU, especially

Fig.13

for military uses.

At the same time, these data show an under-use of fixed installations for Conversion and Enrichment, which could therefore absorb any increase in demand, at least for an initial phase.

- Increase in nuclear electricity generation capacity and coverage of fuel demand**

(Fig. 14) In terms of transition, among the scenarios developed by the OECD for the expected generation (electricity) capacity from nuclear sources, it seems reasonable to assume the highest scenario, which moreover could require an upward revision, given the general re-orientation towards “nuclear power”.

Fig.14

(Slide 15) Until 2024, the coverage of such a scenario to ensure the transition can rely on commercial stocks, but the further one goes into the future, the more it involves the use of different sources of supply. Some of these sources are not yet specified and constitute a big question mark (???) in Fig. 15) on the future coverage of energy demand. Therefore, it is reasonable to think that it will be necessary not only to make full use of the existing uranium mines, which will have decreasing production over time, the use of those under development, foreseen in perspective and those already planned or reactivated, but requires a strong contribution from "unspecified" supply sources yet, but to be specified! It therefore appears rational to assume that such an unspecified source may also involve military inventories as well as commercial ones that will want to exploit that 95% of material that can become fertile contained in the spent fuel or fertilizable materials from other sources. It follows the great impetus that should receive all research in the nuclear field for the development of innovative technologies along the lines of what is already happening in the Eastern world. It is hoped that the EU will take this signal and act accordingly without hesitation.

Upper Scenario for uranium supply and demand, tU

Source:

<https://world-nuclear.org/getmedia/9a2f9405-1135-407a-85c8-480e2365bee7/nuclear-fuel-report-2021-expanded-summary.pdf.aspx>

Fig.15

(Tab.16) In the context outlined so far, it seems necessary in our opinion for the EU to launch a specific **Sustainability and Security Report for an energy transition that clearly includes nuclear energy and the choices necessary to complete it, country by country and overall for the whole EU**, but which is not limited only to the handling & management aspects, but rather looks holistically at every aspect, including those of the possible supply chains, their safety and production sufficiency, along the lines of the 2020 Report of which is reported below a risk analysis, perhaps to be reviewed. The role of nuclear research in this context is crucial and ignoring it would be culpable.

No.	Risk	Probability of occurrence	Impact on supply	Duration of impact	Final score
1	Lack of transport hubs open to nuclear shipments	3.20	2.30	2.00	7.36
2	Lack of investments in conversion facilities	3.10	2.20	2.60	6.82
3	Permanent reduction of production and withdrawal from uranium exploration	3.00	2.20	2.70	6.60
4	Lack of harmonisation and multiple regulation in transport authorisation	3.10	2.00	2.10	6.20
5	Temporary suspension of production, or shortage of capacity of conversion	3.00	2.00	1.80	6.00
6	Lack of investment in mines	3.00	1.90	2.70	5.70
7	Temporary suspension of production, or shortages in uranium mines	3.00	1.60	1.50	4.80
8	Security of supply in light of the current political situation, e.g. restrictions on access to nuclear material and related services	2.50	1.90	1.60	4.75
9	Supply disruption resulting from political instability	2.30	2.00	1.80	4.60
10	Overdependence on a single source of supply of fuel fabrication services	2.70	1.70	2.00	4.59

Source:

https://euratom-supply.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-06/2020_Security_report_2.pdf

Tab.16

- **Conclusions**

Based on what is expressed here, the correlation between Nuclear Conversion and Disarmament appears evident to the point that there can be no disarmament without sustainability, security and peace; just as there can be no sustainability, security and peace without disarmament.

The truth has always been and still remains only one: to pursue the real goals of disarmament it is necessary to be aware that the only peaceful way to get rid of the destructive potential of atomic bombs and of fissile material in general is: to be able to "burn" it in nuclear reactors, to produce electricity and heat for district heating, which improve the living conditions of the peoples of the Earth. An obligatory choice, unless wishful thinking, to conserve the nuclear military power available under the pretext of defending oneself, even against large asteroids or a hypothetical alien danger; or more likely for a world hegemonic project.

This is also true in the perspective, far from being immediate and certain, of nuclear fusion as an alternative to fission, a topic on which we should have answers in 2025 from the ITER of Cadarache. And on this issue of fusion, which we also consider of primary importance for a sustainable future and therefore for the necessary researches, like that in the field of fission with innovative reactors, we would like to conclude this analysis. We therefore bring to your attention that our Association www.nuclearforpeace.org holds - through one of its members - ownership of a patent for the experimentation of nuclear fusion with electrostatic confinement. Of this project we will leave in the records of this meeting, in addition to this report, also extensive technical, economic and programmatic documentation, trusting in the interest of any national and international research institutions and of the EU itself.

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• **Reference Doc.s Available on the Web**

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